

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS OF FUTURE MUSIC EDUCATION

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Abstract. The article presents information about the cognitive competence of music education teachers, their ability to obtain information in the educational process, organize their activities in educational systems, and provide themselves with new information. In this process of music education, it was suggested that the cognitive psychology of students should be improved through effective pedagogical approaches in order to regularly update their professional knowledge, gradually develop skills, and subsequently teach as music education teachers, solve problems in their imaginary thinking. Music education also plays an important role in social and personal development. Cognitive competence is important in this topic, and competence ensures that students can easily acquire new knowledge from teachers. The article is devoted to these topical issues.

Key words: Personality, society, thinking, cognitive competence, interdisciplinary thinking, cognitive psychology, cognitive personality, socio-pedagogical aspect.

INTRODUCTION

Intellectual development of a person in the world, effective organization of activities by making the right decision, formation of divergent thinking style, identification of psycho-pedagogical and individual factors of development of visual-spatial strategies in perception and processing of information in the virtual world, manifestation of cognitive competence in the pedagogical process the issues of studying the dynamics of being are gaining urgent importance from a socio-pedagogical point of view. In particular, the factors that ensure the manifestation of synthetic, associative thinking style in non-standard situations by developing the cognitive competence of future music education teachers through interdisciplinary cooperation, the influence of independent cognitive style and activity styles, memory efficiency depending on temperamental characteristics Implementation of work to strengthen development mechanisms remains one of the urgent problems. The problem of interdisciplinarity is "problematic thinking, "offset vision". This does not mean abandoning the acquisition of knowledge in a disciplinary way, but it means supplementing it with methods of interdisciplinary transfer of material that forms interdisciplinary thinking.

Interdisciplinary thinking is the basis for forming a space of knowledge in solving common problems for merging (integrating) disciplinary sciences. The study of these problems should serve as a basis for the formation of a certain type of thinking. The theoretical concepts of one discipline are used by another discipline, this process helps to solve common problems, that is, there is talk of creating common methodological and cognitive approaches in interdisciplinary research.

In the world, the formation of cognitive competence in educational activities, individual differences in the manifestation of student thinking style in the perception and processing of

virtual and social information, differential features in the cognitive style of future music education teachers, memory efficiency, mnemonics, in the state of frustration Scientific research is being conducted on the mechanisms of manifestation of the cognitive style of "impulsivity-reflexivity", issues of developing tolerance to information. In this regard, the essence of cognitive competence, its socio-psychological aspects that determine the individuality of a person, its manifestation in activity and thinking, the levels of pedagogical influence observed in cognitive simplicity and complexity, psychological characteristics of cognitive competence, the influence of the educational process on the development of cognitive competence in students there is a need for scientific research of secret issues. In the advanced research institutes and centers of the world, in particular, the Music Education Center of England, the Center for the Development of Musical Skills by Teaching Violin Performance in Japan, the Center for the Development of Music Education in Hungary, the Center for Singing Education and Research in Germany, Switzerland In addition to increasing the level of scientific-theoretical, pedagogical-psychological and scientific-methodical training of the future music teacher, many scientific and pedagogical studies aimed at developing cognitive competence are being carried out in the centers of musical creativity, the centers for the development of the experience of perception of Russian musical works. In these studies, the methodical system for developing the cognitive competence, artistic-aesthetic taste, ideal and system of views of future music education teachers is being regularly improved.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS.

In the study of ways to improve the technologies for improving the cognitive competence of the future music teacher, not only limited to theoretical and historical bases, but also the results of practical research, foreign and domestic researches were compared, analyzed and studied.

Buni Bronson, Merriman, Ken Robinson, Fisher, Frey, Begetto, Kaufman, Ali, Treffinger (2008) and others from foreign musicologists and pedagogues on improving the professional competence of future music teachers. many studies conducted by, can be seen from their results. From the scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States, great importance is attached to the development of music education through cognitive research: B.S. Gershunsky, V.P. Bezpalko, I.V. Snigirov, B. G. Asafev, B. L. Yavorsky, A. B. Goldenweiser, D. B. Kabalevsky, O. A. Apraktsina, E. B. Abdulin, Yu. It was studied through scientific research conducted by B. Aliev, L. G. Archajnikova, A. N. Leybovich, G. A. Ball, S. E. Shishov.

Among the scientists of our country R.SH.Akhlidinov, R.Kh.Joraev, J.G'.Yoldoshev, U.N.Nishonaliev, D.SH.Shodiev, A.K.Avliyokulov, A.Bekmurodov, Kh.Inoyatov, R.Q.Karimov, X.A.To' Rakulov, M.H. Hasanov, and the scientific researches are focused on the didactic aspects of future music teachers' cognitive development based on DTS, effective pedagogical factors and the problems of organizing monitoring for their application in educational practice. and to implement this process, it was concluded that it is necessary to carry out scientific research on the model of improving the conative competence of future music education teachers and improving its methodological conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Our young people are free thinkers, free from any negative influencing ideas, mind and thinking dependence, can honestly evaluate the events happening in the family and environment and express their free attitude to them, have their progressive thoughts, for example, it is meant to be able to influence family members, classmates, friends, have

intellectual power, diligent, educated, brave and polite. In fact, providing young people with excellent knowledge based on the application of modern methods of pedagogy and psychology and forming free thinking in them, training them for a healthy life and an independent life based on our traditions and customs is a task [1]. Therefore, in the education of young people, it is necessary to constantly develop knowledge and skills in order to become a worthy person of his time. At this point, we want to touch on the subject of human cognitive psychology.

Cognitive psychology studies all mental processes from emotion to cognition, neuroscience, attention, consciousness, learning, memory, concept formation, thinking, imagination, recall, language, emotions, and all possible domains of development and action. contains z. These include all the research that has been done to help us understand the nature of thinking. And this topic involves looking at a person from the outside, based on new tasks, undoubtedly helps to determine the point of view of the intellectual essence of a person. For a more complete and accurate knowledge of the human psyche and the structure and function of the nervous system, we have achieved new logical tools, the introduction of computers, the use of methodological guidelines in the study of human psychology and cultural practices, and the development of cognitive psychology. It was based on the ideas of deep understanding of questions originally developed by Plato, Desartes, Kant and Darwin. Things and events in the surrounding environment, such as the sight, sound, odor distribution, movement, lightness or weight, hardness or softness, serve as an unconditional stimulus signal for animals, which can later become a conditioned reflex.

The word cognitive is derived from the English (Latin) word "cognize", which means to know, understand, understand and think, or "cognition" - to know, to understand. On the other hand, the activity of knowing is a phenomenon related to a person's direct perception and feeling of reality.

Views on the cognitive person and issues of educating such a person cover the period from the distant past to the present day. In particular, Abu Nasr Al-Faroabi (873-950) said, "A person's intellectual ability is naturally prepared to perceive mental details (knowledge of the world) in the state of potential at the time of birth (in the child's brain). But the perceptual abilities are different in different people. Or if people do not have the opportunity to perceive mental nuances, some do not use these opportunities" [2; p. 48]. From these thoughts of the great scholar, it can be understood that people living in society have the qualities of creativity in some sense, but there must be a sufficient environment for these qualities to emerge.

In the world, it is important for a person to create new things during his daily and professional activities, to develop new innovative ideas, to choose an effective way in various unexpected situations, and to make rational decisions. If we look at all fields, including the field of education, we can see new inventions, optimized processes, rapid rejection of innovations, and a rapid increase in the weight of competition in this direction. The basis of these is the human factor, the product of thinking, and its creative qualities. From this point of view, the development of the cognitive competence of future pedagogues, who are the main participants in the educational process in the improvement of the educational system, its goals and tasks in an innovative way, which is considered the most important for the development of society, is gaining urgent importance.

According to the Decree "On the approval of the concession for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" "Increasing the level of

coverage with higher education, based on international standards, highly qualified, creative and systematic thinking, able to make independent decisions training of personnel, creation of necessary conditions for the manifestation of their intellectual abilities and formation as a spiritually mature person" [3; p. 9] has become one of the strategic goals of the development of the higher education system. To increase the competitiveness of graduates of higher education institutions in the labor market, to increase the effectiveness of the educational process by developing the creative competence of pedagogues, to develop the cognitive competence of students, especially future music teachers, and to internationalize the functions of the higher education system in the implementation of these tasks. research based on national requirements is considered as an urgent issue [4].

Formation of specialists with professional cognitive competence is one of the main tasks of the educational system of modern society. Observations and analyzes show that cognition is considered an integral part, direction and aspect of strategic importance in all areas. In the system of higher pedagogical education, it is envisaged to direct the educational process to the individual as the main mechanism for developing the cognitive competence of the future music teacher.

In today's fast-paced era, it is impossible to reach maturity without having a rich imagination, creative ideas, cognitive qualities in a broad sense, and acquiring various sciences and professions.

Summarizing the opinions presented above and based on the analysis of our research, the student's cognitive in relation to the educational process is his unusual thinking, the ability to respond positively to an unexpected situation, be ready for any question and show the most perfect result compared to others, and the educational process is an activity aimed at creating new ideas as a participant. One of the distinctive features of cognitive development during the student period is the formation of specialized cognition during this period. In other words, during this period, the motivation to pursue professional activity is in harmony with the development of their knowledge activity, determination of their lifestyle, and the process of individualization. It is known that any person acquires certain activity experience as a result of the growth of his professional knowledge. Therefore, a person should create and improve his professional experience with his cognitive skills. Students acquire such experiences as a result of education in higher education institutions and enrich them throughout their lives. Therefore, it is appropriate to pay special attention to the acquisition of professional competences and the development of cognitive abilities in the process of education in higher educational institutions.

Each of us perceives reality through our own models or the need to create a coherent picture of the world. If the construction events help to visualize clearly, then maybe it can be saved. If the information is not confirmed, on the contrary, a case may be issued, which is the basis for reconsideration of the subject. Each person has his own constructive system, which he uses to interpret life experiences. People differ in their interpretation of events. Two people, they can be identical twins, have similar views on the phenomenon and interpret them in different ways. Each person understands the truth from the "calling" of their true personal structure. The difference between people is that they interpret events in different ways. George Kelly said, "A person tries to explain the truth in order to predict the events that will affect his life. Private structures predicts the future with its unique system. This is how people's views are explained today. People's behavior is determined by how they predict

future events. This means that a person can know how to understand your personal experience. George Kelly As we humans construct our own constructs, we need to know the proper identity. Social relations consist primarily of one person's attempts to understand how another person realizes reality. In order to have an effective influence, people must understand each other, and their subsequent actions cannot be unbalanced and unusual. If it is formed, an immediate interest is needed to change this situation, to establish knowledge and system, internal stability.

CONCLUSION

In short, cognitive competence is a skill that includes learning skills such as identifying, analyzing, solving problems, and acquiring new information. Cognitive competence for music education teachers to easily learn the music-related information of students, to adequately support them in the educational process, to reflect on and teach their musical information comes from upgrading the learning capabilities. This competence increases the ability of music education students to acquire new knowledge through analytical thinking.

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